

Job stability can help retain early-career teachers

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Summary

1. Early-career teacher attrition is an important contributor to teacher shortages in Flanders.
2. A first-year teacher's average contract lasts around four months. Fewer than 7.5% of starters work only with contracts covering a full school year.
3. Short contracts are strongly associated with early attrition.
4. A permanent substitute system entitled 'teacher platform' offers job security for a full school year, but its effect on retention is modest. Platform teachers often still face fragmented replacement assignments.
5. The estimated cost of retaining one additional full-time teacher through the teacher platform lies between €650,000 and €1,950,000.
6. Policy should focus not only on job security, but also on reducing fragmentation in early-career teaching assignments.

1. Introduction

Teacher shortages remain a major challenge for Flemish education. Around 3,500 full-time teachers are missing to fill all regular and replacement assignments. One important reason is early-career attrition: more than one in four qualified beginning teachers stops teaching within five years. Although teacher attrition is not higher than in other sectors, it is especially problematic in education because schools already face persistent staffing shortages.

A key challenge for beginning teachers is the instability of their first assignments. Teaching

is often associated with long-term job security, but many new teachers spend their first years combining short replacement contracts, sometimes interrupted by periods without work. This creates two problems. First, starters experience uncertainty: they may not know where or when their next contract will start. Second, their work becomes fragmented: they move between classes, grades, subjects and schools, often with little preparation time. This can weaken their connection with pupils and colleagues, while increasing workload and stress.

To address this problem, the Flemish Government introduced the teacher platform in 2018. Through this measure, school groups receive additional funding to hire "platform

teachers” for a full school year. These teachers are then available for replacement assignments within the school group. When they are not replacing absent teachers, they carry out useful pedagogical tasks, such as co-teaching or preparing learning materials. Similar permanent substitute systems exist in other countries.

This policy brief examines whether job stability helps retain early-career teachers and whether the teacher platform is an effective solution. The findings are important for policymakers because teacher shortages are not only about attracting new teachers. They are also about keeping those who have already entered the profession. The evidence shows that stability matters, but also that not all forms of stability are equally effective. A full-year contract alone is not enough if the actual work remains highly fragmented.

2. Data and Methodology

The study uses unique administrative data covering more than 50,000 qualified beginning teachers in primary and secondary education in Flanders between 2008-2009 and 2021-2022. The dataset includes information on contract start and end dates, workload, qualifications, school characteristics and individual teacher background.

Job stability is measured in three ways: the average duration of contracts, the time spent without a teaching contract between the first and last contract in a school year, and whether teachers have obtained a permanent appointment. The study then examines how these measures are related to teacher retention.

To evaluate the teacher platform, platform teachers are compared with similar regular teachers. The analysis uses statistical methods

that control as much as possible for differences in teacher profiles, schools and assignments. The study also examines whether secondary schools that could participate in the platform had fewer unfilled replacement hours than other schools.

The results should be interpreted with some caution. The methods allow for a strong comparison between groups, but they cannot fully guarantee causality. The brief therefore focuses on the size, direction and policy relevance of the estimated effects.

3. Results

The study shows that early-career teaching is highly unstable. In their first year, teachers have contracts lasting on average 129 days, or just over four months. Only 7.5% of first-year teachers have contracts that, on average, last more than 300 days. Between their first and last teaching contract in a school year, beginning teachers spend around 7% of their time without a contract. More than one in ten qualified first-year teachers no longer works as a teacher in the following year.

Stability improves over time. By the fifth year, the average contract duration almost doubles to 233 days. Time without a contract falls to 1.3%, and some teachers begin to obtain permanent appointments. Annual attrition falls to around 4%. The chart on page 3 shows this pattern clearly: as contract duration increases and time without a contract decreases, the probability of leaving teaching also declines.

Longer contracts are strongly linked to retention. A teacher whose contracts are, on average, 100 days longer has a retention probability that is 2.2 to 4.6 percentage points higher. Contract duration is even a stronger predictor of retention than having the

required qualification, a short commute or a permanent appointment.

However, the teacher platform has only a modest effect. Platform teachers have a retention probability that is only 0.3 to 0.9 percentage points higher than comparable regular teachers, and not all estimates are statistically significant. The likely reason is that the platform reduces work uncertainty but not fragmentation. Platform teachers often take more very short replacements and work in more schools.

The platform may also reduce unfilled replacement hours, but the evidence is mixed. Estimates range from 19 to 77 additional filled teaching hours per participating school. The cost-effectiveness is therefore limited: retaining one additional full-time teacher through the platform is estimated to cost between €656,647 and €1,968,940.

4. Policy Recommendations

1. Reduce fragmentation, not only uncertainty. Beginning teachers need stability in their actual assignment, not only in their contract. A full-year contract can help, but its effect is limited when teachers still move constantly between short replacement tasks, classes and schools.

2. Give starters more regular teaching assignments. A structural solution is to assign beginning teachers more often to stable classroom roles, while more experienced teachers take on replacement work. This is already legally possible within the teacher platform, but is rarely used in practice.

3. Use targeted incentives for hard-to-staff schools. Teacher shortages are not evenly distributed. Shortages are much larger in places such as Brussels and other urban areas.

Because job stability currently helps these schools attract teachers, offering the same stability everywhere may weaken their advantage. More targeted measures, such as premiums for teachers in shortage areas, are needed.

4. Reconsider the cost-effectiveness of the teacher platform. The platform provides useful support to schools when teachers perform pedagogical tasks outside replacement work. If this is a core goal, the measure may be valuable. But if the main goal is reducing teacher shortages, the costs are high compared with the retention effects.

5. Build evaluation into new policies from the start. Pilot projects should be designed with quantitative evaluation in mind. Random or phased access to new measures can help policymakers measure effects more reliably before large budgets are permanently committed.

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EFFEct is an impact-driven research project aiming to enhance the quality of education in the EU by providing evidence-based policy recommendations and conducting rigorous research on the education policies of individual EU member states.

Further Information:

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